

Research Article

The Effect of Agro-forestry (*Leucaena leucocephala*) Tree Pruning's in Priming Media as a Nutrient Source in Early Crop Establishment for Maize (*Zea mays*) in Zimbabwe

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ABSTRACT

Maize crop establishment is a major problem in smallholder farming. A field experiment was carried out in Hurungwe district (Zimbabwe) in the 2011/12 growing season to determine the role of agroforestry tree pruning's (*Leucaena leucocephala*) in priming media for crop establishment. In the experiment, concentrations of 0, 50, 100, 150 and 200g l⁻¹ were used in varying seed with soaking periods of 16, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours in priming media. The results showed that percentage germination, radicle length and the germination time were significantly (p<0.05) affected by soaking period and pruning concentrations. Shoot dry mass of maize was not significantly affected (p<0.05) by pruning concentration and soaking period. Results suggest that the optimum concentration of pruning required for initiation of above ground plant growth falls within the 100-150g l⁻¹ range. Furthermore, increase in concentration resulted in progressive decline in the germination rate. Soaking seeds for 24 hours at 100g l⁻¹ improved the crop establishment. Smallholder farmers can utilize a pruning concentration of 100g l⁻¹ for 24 hours to enhance nutrient availability to the seed. In addition, use of the amended priming media is encouraged to enhance early crop germination and offset the effect of inherent soil acidity and infertility that characterize most parts of the country.

INTRODUCTION

Most Zimbabwean soils are nutrient deficient and are degrading at a rapid rate. The granite parent material that makes up these sandy soils is deficient in organic matter and therefore low in nitrogen (0.02-0.05%) and phosphorus (Nyamapfene, 1991). The relative exchange capacities of these soils are also low indicating high levels of acidity as a result of low clay content (Grant, 1970). In smallholder farming systems, the continuous production of a single crop year after year with little or very low external inputs into the farming system has also resulted in the continued decline in productivity of these crops, particularly the staple crop which is maize (Grant, 1980).

Maize is an important crop in Zimbabwe. This is as a result of a number of reasons that include: achieving food self sufficiency; it is an ingredient in processing industry, it occupies more than half the cropland in natural region II as well as the fact that it is preferred over more drought tolerant crops such as millet and sorghum (Phillips *et al*, 1998). In Zimbabwe's smallholder farming sector, poor soil fertility has resulted in a declining per capita food production particularly maize. This is as a result of monocropping, low and inappropriate use of inorganic and organic fertilizers and crop removal without return of nutrients into the system (Sakala and Mhango, 2002) and use of animal manure in some cases as fuel rather than as a nutrient source (Cooper *et al*, 1998). Fertilizer use is also sparse among smallholder farmers as a result of high cost from the suppliers (Mapfumo and Giller, 2001), lack of credit and delays in delivery of the fertilizers (Nkala, 2011). Nitrogen, phosphorus and sulphur are the limiting factors. The most critical fertilizer is nitrogenous and is required in larger amounts but it is often lost from the farming system through leaching and runoff (Kasasa, Mpepereki and Giller, 1998). In addition, farmers can not afford to implement long term soil management and improvement strategies because of lack of secure tenure, access to credit and unfavourable pricing policies on crops that they produce (Nkala, 2011). Physiological factors that affect maize production are delays in germination and low seed viability (Hanegave *et al*, 2011) which result in patchy plant stands. Highly vigorous seeds germinate rapidly, uniformly and are able to withstand environmental adversity after sowing while weaker seeds do not germinate uniformly. The wide ranges in seedling emergence decrease the amount of harvestable plants per hectare (Harris, 2006).

Organic materials can be a relatively important source of nutrients for smallholder farmers that lack the financial resources to purchase sufficient mineral nitrogen (Palm *et al*, 1998). Many studies have shown that agroforestry prunings or litter can supply sufficient nitrogen to meet demand with the notable exception of phosphorus (Mafongoya *et al*, 1998).

Small doses of inorganic fertilizers can be used in combination with manure to reduce the amount spent on inorganic fertilizers (Carberry *et al*, 2004). Organic inputs are often proposed as alternatives to mineral fertilizers.

Alternative approaches have become necessary since the traditional organic inputs such as crop residues, woodland leaf litter and animal manures do not meet crop nutrient demand over large areas because of the limited quantities available, low nutrient content of the materials and high labour demands for processing and application (Palm, Murwira and Carter, 1998). Farmers in Zimbabwe fall between two extremes from the organic to inorganic continuum, with smallholder farmers using predominantly the organic forms. Crop yields fall short of their potential because of inadequate nutrient inputs, the appropriate quality of the organic materials and inefficient combinations (Palm *et al*, 1998).

As a result of limited nitrogen supply capacity of sandy soils (Grant, 1981), seedling establishment, poor growth and ultimately low yield is a common problem among smallholder farmers. Severe nitrogen deficiency often arises very early in the cropping cycle, hampering early crop establishment and subsequent growth. Good crop establishment is one of the major challenges in crop production under rain fed smallholder agriculture (Murungu *et al*, 2003) because of inadequate moisture and low nutrient quantities in the soil. Seeds that emerge faster produce a more even plant stand and grow more vigorously (Harris, 2006). Good crop establishment is essential for the efficient use of growth resources (Harris, 1996). A good stand establishment is of paramount importance because patchy stands result in low yields and, often, crop failure. Even if sparse crops can be re-sown, it is expensive and can lead poor farmers into crippling debt (Harris, 2002). According to a study carried out in Zimbabwe, seed priming advanced the emergence of maize and reduced the time taken for 50% emergence by about 12 hours. In another study with sorghum seed priming hastened germination, maturity, harvest and to some extent reduced the effect of a dry spell as well as pest and disease incidence (Ramamurthy *et al*, 2005). Priming, a technique that involves soaking the seeds in water, usually overnight, before sowing can reduce this time (Murungu, Chiduzo, Nyamufagata, Clark and Whalley, 2003). Mineral fertilizers such as zinc sulphate can be dissolved in water to prepare a priming media. Priming water can also be used as a media for boosting supplements (Harris, 2003).

The inhibitory cost of nitrogenous fertilizers in smallholder farming means that very few farmers can afford reasonable quantities required to increase crop yields beyond subsistence levels (Nhamo and Murwira, 1997). The fertilizer use patterns in Zimbabwe also lead to the development of soil acidity, particularly in depleted sands with low buffering capacity hence crop residues are continuously removed (Mapfumo and Giller, 2001). Mafongoya and Nair (1997) showed that incorporation of nitrogen rich tree prunings might improve nitrogen recovery from rapid biomass decomposition and nitrogen release resulting in increased crop yields. However, adoption of such agroforestry practice is low because of high labour demands and low amounts of tree prunings available to farmers. This then calls for innovative ways

into the utilization of agroforestry tree prunings for biomass utilization hence soaking of ground agroforestry tree litter in water to form a priming media would be advantageous in that smaller quantities of biomass would be used on seeds to be planted in the whole field. On farm seed priming as a method of pruning application may boost the nutrient content of the seed and enhance early growth, hence timely capture of nutrients and a subsequent higher yield. The aim of this study was therefore to determine effective alternative methods for the use of nitrogen rich agroforestry tree prunings in seed priming as a method of enhancing germination and subsequent maize seedling establishment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiment was carried out in Makonde District with maize as a test crop. The site is located in Agro-ecological zone 2. It has recorded up to 576 pentads over a thirty year period. A rainy pentad is defined as the centre one of three five-day periods. The mean annual temperature is 19°C and the arable lands are flat with slopes of 2% or less. The soils in the experimental site are generally sandy. A random sample was used to collect the soil samples. *Leucaena leucocephala* tree biomass was used. The samples of biomass had the following composition : 4.76% Nitrogen, 0.246% Phosphorus and 1.285% Potassium. The soil samples were sent for analysis at the chemistry and soil research institute and the texture was medium grained sandy with a pH of 4.5.

The objectives of the experiment were to:

Evaluate the potential role of agro forestry tree prunings in seed priming as an early nutrient supply source for seedling establishment.

Determine the ideal concentration of tree prunings in priming media for the maximum dry matter production by maize seedlings.

The experiment was carried out by chopping and soaking *Leucaena leucocephala* biomass in water for varying periods of 16, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours to make a priming media with each pruning applied at the following rates: 0g l⁻¹, 50g l⁻¹, 100g l⁻¹, 150g l⁻¹ and 200g l⁻¹ of water. Hundred seeds were then soaked at the same time with the *Leucaena* biomass. The seeds were surface dried for easy handling in preparation for the germination tests. The experiment was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with the treatment replicated three times testing the effect of pruning concentration in the priming media on germination and radicle emergence of maize.

The second stage of the experiment was a 5*5 factorial experiment laid out in a CRD and also replicated three times and the ultimate factors were as follows:

Factor 1: Pruning concentration at 5 levels: 0g l⁻¹ of water (pure water), 50g l⁻¹ of water, 100g l⁻¹, 150g l⁻¹ and 200g l⁻¹ of water.

Factor 2: Soaking period at 5 levels: 16, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hrs.

After the various concentrations of the priming media were prepared, maize seeds were soaked in each priming media for 16, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hrs. Seeds from each treatment were surface dried and immediately planted in moist soils in the field. The plant spacing was 30x45cm. The plots were frequently watered but also avoiding water logging. The time (in days) taken for the maize crop to emerge was noted.

Data Collection and Analysis

Number of days to germination, radicle length and germination percentage were measured to determine the effect of seed priming.

Maize seed time to germination, radicle length and germination percentage were analysed as a 5*5 factorial experiment arranged in a Complete Randomised Design (CRD) testing the effect of pruning concentration and soaking period. Experimental data was subjected to ANOVA using Genstat Release 3.2. The level of significance was at p<0.05.

RESULTS

The effect of the interaction between pruning concentration and soaking period on maize germination percentage

The concentration of pruning material significantly affected germination percentage while soaking period had also an effect on maize seed germination (Fig 1). There was also an interaction between soaking period and the pruning concentration. As pruning concentration increases there is an increase in germination percentage up to 100g l⁻¹. Beyond this concentration, germination begins to subside. The highest germination rates were obtained between 16 and 24 hours of soaking, giving 100% and 99% germination respectively. Generally 24 hours of soaking had the highest germination percentages across all the various concentrations of *Leucaena* prunings (Fig 1). For soaking periods 48, 72 and 96 hours, there is a progressive decline of germination percentage with increased concentration of *Leucaena* prunings. The rate of germination was reduced.

Fig. 1: The interaction between *Leucaena* concentration and days of soaking on maize germination percentage

The effect of the interaction between *Leucaena* concentration and soaking period on radicle elongation of maize
 Priming with agroforestry tree prunings promoted radicle elongation in maize seeds. The lengths of maize radicle increased with increasing concentration of the priming media up to 100g l⁻¹ where further increase in concentration resulted in a reduced rate of growth of

radicle. The highest length of 3.35 cm was noted at 24 hrs of soaking whereas maize seeds primed in pure water (0 g l⁻¹ of water) had a length at 3.25 cm at that same period of soaking. As the concentration of *Leucaena* increases there is a decline in the radicle lengths. The lowest radicle length of 0.4cm was noted at 200g l⁻¹ of water at 96 hrs of soaking (Fig 2).

Fig. 2: The interaction between *Leucaena* concentration and soaking period on maize radicle length

The effects of the interaction between *Leucaena* concentration and soaking period on number of days to emergence of maize seeds

There was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the number of days to emergence between seeds soaked for 16 hrs and 24 hrs up to a concentration of 100 g l^{-1} . For 16 hrs of soaking, the number of days of germination increased when the seeds were soaked in a priming

media of 200 g l^{-1} , meaning it took longer for the germination process. At 48 and 72 hrs of soaking, there is also no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in the number of days to germination at low concentration of *Leucaena* (between 50 and 100 g l^{-1}). When the seeds were soaked for longer periods of time (96 hrs), they generally had slow germination across all levels of *Leucaena* concentration (Fig 3).

Fig. 3: The interaction between *Leucaena* concentration and soaking period on days to emergence of maize seedlings

Effects of Pruning Concentration on Maize Shoot Dry Mass

Maize shoots dry mass increased with increasing concentration of pruning material. The highest shoot dry mass was obtained at 100 g l^{-1} which was not significantly

different ($P < 0.05$) from the seeds soaked in 150 g l^{-1} . The seeds soaked in concentrations of 0; 50 and 200 g l^{-1} had lower shoot dry masses that were not statistically different though lower than those that were soaked at 100 g l^{-1} and 150 g l^{-1} (Fig 4).

Fig. 4: Effect of pruning concentration on maize shoot dry mass

Effects of soaking period on maize shoot dry mass in poor soils

Soaking period did not significantly ($P < 0.05$) have an effect on the maize shoot dry mass at 16, 48, 72 and 96

hrs. However, a significantly ($P > 0.05$) higher shoot mass was obtained in maize seeds that were soaked for 24 hrs (Fig 5). As the period of soaking increases from 24 hrs, there is a progressive decline in the maize shoot dry mass.

Fig. 5: The effects of soaking period on shoot dry mass

DISCUSSION

The effect of the interaction between pruning concentration and soaking period on maize germination percentage

The concentration of pruning material significantly affected germination percentage while soaking period had also an effect on maize seed germination (Fig 1). There was also an interaction between soaking period and the pruning concentration. As pruning concentration increases there is an increase in germination percentage up to 100g l⁻¹. Beyond this concentration, germination begins to subside (Fig 1). This was probably because of the optimum amount of nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and other micro-nutrients such as zinc and boron that were made available by priming using agroforestry tree species in the priming media. This compares to the work of Muhammad *et al*, (2008) who concluded that nutrient seed priming significantly increased the content of micronutrients in the soya beans seeds up to twenty times. In other studies, priming was well known as a mechanism for providing some starter phosphorus to crop seeds and maize, providing micronutrients such as Molybdenum, Zinc and Boron to crops and improving the performance of seeds germinating in saline affected soils (DFID, 2011). This could be due to increased salinity of the priming water with increased period of soaking that had affected some of the seedlings such that they could not germinate fast or rather failed to germinate. This could imply that the period of soaking *Leucaena* prunings was a contributing factor in determining the germination rate as the physico-chemical processes that were required for the pre-germination processes.

The effect of the interaction between *Leucaena* concentration and soaking period on radicle elongation of maize

As the concentration of *Leucaena* increased there was a decline in the radicle lengths. The lowest radicle length of 0.4cm was noted at 200g l⁻¹ of water at 96 hrs of soaking (Fig 2). This could be because the organic acids that were produced on decomposition of pruning material inhibited rapid elongation of the radicle. At higher concentration and at longer soaking periods, these organic acids were present in higher levels which could have been toxic to the developing radicle thereby hampering its expansion hence elongation.

The effects of the interaction between *Leucaena* concentration and soaking period on number of days to emergence of maize seeds

When the seeds were soaked for longer periods of time (96 hrs), there was generally slower germination across all levels of *Leucaena* concentration (Fig 3). This also could be due to the production of excess amounts of organic acids that could have affected the germination process or the fact that the acids could have an antagonistic effect on the growth hormones that were responsible for initiating the germination process.

Effects of Pruning Concentration on Maize Shoot Dry Mass

Maize shoots dry mass increased with increasing concentration of pruning material. This could have been due to the fact that the optimum nutrients required for seed germination were produced in the priming media with a concentration between 100 g l⁻¹ and 150g l⁻¹ that resulted in early germination and more vigorous growth of the seedling.

Effects of soaking period on maize shoot dry mass in poor soils

Soaking period did not significantly have an effect on the maize shoot dry mass at 16, 48, 72 and 96 hrs. The results could have been due to the fact that at 16 hrs the release of nutrients from the priming material was not adequate to produce high shoot mass while at 24 hrs, it could have been the optimum soaking period that produced the ideal quantities of nutrients from the *Leucaena* which was required for shoot growth. As the period of soaking increased from 24 hrs, there was a progressive decline in the maize shoot dry mass. This could have been due to the reduction in radicle development as the period of soaking increased. Increased number of days for germination, led to a reduction in shoot development, elongation and ultimately dry mass.

CONCLUSIONS

From the results of the study, it can be concluded that agroforestry prunings, when used in priming media enhances early seed germination compared to priming in pure water. The concentration of the priming media has an influence on early germination and subsequent growth of seedling where the best results were produced at 100g l⁻¹ of water. Soaking period (*Leucaena* biomass and

maize seeds) has an effect on maize seed germination and eventual seedling growth. There is also an interaction between soaking period and the concentration of the priming media.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended that farmers should prime their maize seeds prior to planting in an amended media containing *Leucaena* biomass, since this enhances early germination that can ensure early crop establishment and an even crop stand that is currently a challenge in smallholder farming systems. Smallholder farmers should also prime their maize seeds for 24 hrs as this has proved to produce optimum results in a priming media with a concentration of 100g l⁻¹ of *Leucaena* biomass compared to the traditional method of planting seeds where they just take seeds from their bag and plant them without first priming them. Farmers should invest in the production of agroforestry trees species since it has a number of uses on the farm, among them providing a cheaper source of nutrients for early crop germination and root development.

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